

EDUCATION AND SOCIAL CHANGE CS AND EDUCATION

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Abstract:

It is the process of social and economic change that transforms a human group from an agrarian society into an industrial one. It is a part of a wider modernization process, where social change and economic development are closely related with technological innovation, particularly with the development of large-scale energy and metallurgy production. It is the extensive organization of an economy for the purpose of manufacturing.

Keywords: *Industrialization*

New concepts of industrialization

It should be borne in mind that Peter Raggatt did not refer to these Fordist characteristics to eulogise the *Open University* but to criticize it. According to Raggatt, the Fordism of the *Open University*, and of course, of other distance teaching universities, is an *obsolete model*. He is not alone in this opinion but finds support from authors such as Campion (1995), Campion and Renner (1982) and Farnes (1993)

Neo-industrialization:

Neo-industrialization or neo-Fordism has led to many changes in working life. The characteristic slogans here are *high product innovation*, *high process variability*, but at the same time, *low degrees of responsibility for employees* (Badham & Mathews 1989, quoted by Campion & Renner 1992, 12). The endeavour to achieve product innovation and process variability is a reaction to the development of the market and the changes in demand. It is possible at present because on the one hand the demands of consumers with more spending

power have become higher, more specific and more varied, and on the other hand production and distribution of goods have been adapted to meet this because they have to a large extent been computerised. The aim is no longer to produce the same goods of the same quality at the lowest possible price for as many consumers as possible with the same needs. As we know, Ford sold more than 15 million copies of the same car model. This method of production led to a great equalisation of consumption.

Pedagogical consequences:

In the context of this work the importance of the concepts of industrialised and post-industrialized teaching and learning sketched in here depends on whether and how far they are helpful for the planning development, control and interpretation of distance education.

This question is often put by sceptics who are unable to see how concepts that work with terms from industrial sociology - or, even worse, from the field of industrial production itself - can comprise pedagogical circumstances and reproduce them. To them, what happens in factories and lecture halls seems utterly disparate and incommensurable. In fact, it does appear to be difficult to derive starting points from these concepts, for example for the selection and evaluation of learning aims and contents, which is a main concern of humanist pedagogics. First of all a general assessment: many decisions that are taken in the planning, development and revision of teaching and learning systems in distance education in compliance with and taking account of criteria of industrialisation, may first of all serve as the control of the overall process, but can at the same time have an effect on the ways and means with which university teachers teach and students learn. Thus, questions of pedagogics in the narrow sense come into play once again.

The concept of industrialized teaching and learning :

The following specific pedagogical effects can be seen above all here:

- It opens up a macro-pedagogical perspective to those taking part in the planning and development of distance education. While traditional pedagogics focused during planning and preparation above all micro-pedagogically on the interaction between

teachers and students, the view here is extended to cover the totality of all activities of the participants.

- For students it provides deep impressions of the connection between *all* teaching and learning activities and their integration in the process. The teaching and learning process does not start at the beginning of a lecture or seminar. It starts much earlier. And it does not end when students leave the lecture hall or the seminar room, but much later. The division of labour leads to the following sequence: planning, development, distribution, presentation, counselling and evaluation phases. These are all connected to and affect one another.
- The greatest effect of industrialised teaching is, however, a far-reaching change in *teaching behaviour* and perhaps even more in *learning behaviour*. Where specialisation based on the division of labour reduces university teachers to subject-matter specialists and requires distribution of teaching matter with the help of technical media and enables isolated initiated self-study which can only be interrupted occasionally by face-to-face communication with others, these are considerable changes in the field of pedagogics.
- The concept makes it easier for participants to behave in *conformity with the system* when teaching and learning. Industrialised teaching and learning is constituted through the interplay of many system elements. Only if we prepare ourselves for this and see ourselves as part of this type of system can we be successful in avoiding dysfunctional pedagogical actions. Those who adhere to the attitudes and ideas of pre-industrial teaching will certainly come to grief with them in distance education. The concepts of industrialized teaching and learning help us to recognise and avoid mixing elements of structurally completely different systems.
- Seen from a macro-pedagogical point of view the direct effects on teaching and learning are particularly serious and obvious. If industrialised working methods mean that tens or even hundreds of thousands are provided with an opportunity to continue their education by studying, although they would never have been able to do this in a conventional system, the effects on adult education and pedagogics cannot be overestimated, even if support for classes remote from the educational system through distance education is at present no longer *en vogue*.
- For teaching and learning itself, the development of courses on a basis of the division of labour and through the cooperation of specialists is extremely important because

high quality material is created which is pedagogically suitable, reflects the latest levels of research and is presented particularly effectively.

- The development of *closed* curricula and teaching and learning models and learning in paths that are planned and provided for, is benefited. This makes the development of *open* curricula more difficult. Basically, there are not really any plans for taking off down self-chosen learning paths, creating a flexible system of multi-faceted learning programmes using different situations, media, institutions and taking account of the life and work situation of students. Open learning, in the real sense of the word, cannot take place.

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